

EXPLORING THE APPLICATIONS OF BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY IN FAST-MOVING CONSUMER GOODS SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

In an era where digital transformations are reshaping industries, blockchain technology stands out for its potential to revolutionise supply chain management in the Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) sector. This technology's decentralised, transparent, and immutable characteristics promise to address some of the perennial challenges FMCG supply chains face, such as product traceability, transparency, and efficiency. This research delves deeper into these promises, aiming to explore both the theoretical applications and the pragmatic challenges associated with blockchain's integration into FMCG supply chains. Drawing from an extensive literature review and gearing up for a comprehensive empirical survey, we aim to gauge industry sentiments, expectations, and apprehensions. Given the transformative potential of blockchain and the FMCG sector's vast reach, the outcomes of this research may hold significant implications not only for industry stakeholders but also for consumers at large. Through this study, we aspire to craft a roadmap for FMCG entities keen on leveraging blockchain, accentuating the nuances, prerequisites, and strategic alignments essential for successful adoption.

Keywords: Blockchain, Fast-Moving Consumer Goods, Supply Chain, Traceability, Transparency, Cost Reduction

1. INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary global economic tapestry, blockchain technology, initially conceived as an underpinning for cryptocurrencies, has burgeoned into a paragon of disruption and innovation across myriad industrial landscapes (Daghighi and Shoushtari, 2023). Recognised for its cardinal principles of immutable traceability, unassailable security, and heightened transparency, blockchain anchors a transformative potential to recalibrate existing operational and transactional paradigms (Hakim and Bahari, 2021). Within the multifaceted confines of the Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) industry – an arena orchestrated around the pivotal tenets of rapid inventory turnover, succinct delivery timelines, and unwavering reliability of supply chains – the integration of blockchain is not merely an innovation but, arguably, an emergent imperative (Tasnim, Hamid and Nadarajah, 2023). The FMCG sector, oscillating rhythmically to the pulsations of consumer demand, is frequently ensnared by challenges such as combating counterfeiting, ensuring transparent and auditable transaction trajectories, and circumventing inefficiencies spawned by antiquated, manual processes (Chinna, 2016). These challenges are exacerbated by the sector's intrinsic complexity, marked by its expansive, often globalised, supply networks and the imperative for precise, timely coordination among myriad stakeholders – from manufacturers and suppliers to logistics providers and retailers (Jacobs and Mafini, 2019). Furthermore, in an epoch where digitalisation not only thrives but dictates

market dynamics, the insatiable consumer appetite for enhanced transparency, ethical corporate conduct, and environmentally conscientious practices amplifies the exigency for FMCG entities to refine and indeed, revolutionise their supply chain management methodologies (Hennelly *et al.*, 2020).

Blockchain, in this context, emerges as a potent antidote to an array of these entrenched challenges. These proffering solutions extend beyond mere operational efficiency to encapsulate trust, verification, and ethical visibility within supply chain transactions and processes (Emmanuel *et al.*, 2023). The immutable nature of blockchain ensures that once a transaction is recorded within the ledger, it is impervious to alteration, thereby fortifying traceability and substantiating the integrity of product journeys from inception to consumer (Alam, 2023a). Concurrently, blockchain architecture's decentralised and distributed essence bolsters transparency, providing all stakeholders with an unobscured view of transaction histories and product trajectories, mitigating fraud, counterfeiting, and inconsistent information risks.

This entwinement of technological prowess and pragmatic applicability renders blockchain not merely a tool for enhanced supply chain management within the FMCG sector. Still, it positions it as a conduit through which the industry can navigate towards a future that is robust,

transparent, and intrinsically aligned with the nuanced demands of both the market and the contemporary consumer. Therefore, as we delve into the forthcoming chapters, this research endeavours to untangle the complexities, explore the potentialities, and illuminate the challenges of intertwining blockchain technology within the dynamic, ever-evolving realm of FMCG supply chain management, thereby crafting a narrative that is deeply embedded in empirical analysis and practically relevant insights.

Problem Statement

With its promise of transparency and traceability, blockchain presents a significant opportunity for the FMCG industry, particularly in supply chain management. While the potential advantages are vast, FMCG companies often grapple with the challenges of blockchain implementation, including technical complexities, organisational resistance, and potentially high costs. Despite the burgeoning interest in this technology, there's a scarcity of literature that profoundly explores the tangible impacts, both positive and negative, of blockchain within the specific context of FMCG supply chains. This gap emphasises the need for empirical research to understand the real-world benefits and challenges FMCG companies face in blockchain adoption.

Purpose of the Study

The primary aim of this study is to delve into the effects, both advantages and challenges, of integrating blockchain technology within FMCG supply chain management. Through empirical research, this study aims to provide insights into the real-world application of blockchain in this context, identifying areas where it adds value in traceability, transparency, operational efficiency, and cost-effectiveness. Simultaneously, it highlights the potential barriers and pitfalls FMCG companies might encounter during its implementation. Through this dual lens, the research will provide FMCG companies with a comprehensive understanding of blockchain adoption's potential rewards and risks in their supply chains.

Research Questions

This study seeks to answer the following pivotal research questions:

1. RQ1: How does integrating blockchain technology enhance traceability and transparency within FMCG supply chain management?
2. RQ2: What are the discernible impacts of blockchain technology on operational efficiency and cost reduction in FMCG supply chains?
3. RQ3: What challenges and barriers do FMCG companies encounter during the implementation and operation of blockchain within their supply chains?

In responding to these questions, this research aspires to curate a comprehensive, nuanced understanding of blockchain's potential, limitations, and multifaceted impacts within the FMCG sector's supply chain management, thereby contributing substantively to academic discourse and practical managerial strategy within the industry.

Overview of Blockchain Technology

Since its inception in 2008, blockchain technology has transcended its initial application in cryptocurrency, demonstrating extensive applicability and disruption across diverse sectors (Shuaib, Alam, *et al.*, 2022). The fundamental blockchain architecture is characterised by a decentralised ledger, which records transactions across multiple nodes in a network, ensuring that data is transparent but also immutable and secure (Alam, 2023b). This decentralised network operates on a consensus algorithm, where alterations or additions to the blockchain necessitate verification by multiple participants, thereby safeguarding against fraudulent activities and unauthorised data manipulation. Distributed ledger technology, underlined by cryptographic security, encapsulates the potential to reimagine transactions, information sharing, and trust across many operational landscapes (Shuaib, Hassan, Usman, Alam, Bakar, *et al.*, 2022).

Adoption of Blockchain in Various Industries

Blockchain technology, having demonstrated its capacity to overhaul transactional and operational norms, has been embraced and trialled across various industries (Alam *et al.*, 2021) including finance, healthcare (Alam *et al.*, 2023), energy (Khubrani and Alam, 2023), logistics, education (Siddiqui, Fakhreldin and Alam, 2021) and the public sector. In finance, blockchain forms the bedrock of cryptocurrencies and is increasingly being explored for cross-border transactions, smart contracts, and decentralised finance (DeFi) applications (Shuaib, Hassan, Usman, Alam, Bhatia, *et al.*, 2022). The healthcare sector explores blockchain to ensure the integrity and privacy of patient data, streamline insurance claims, and manage drug traceability (Alam *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, logistics and supply chains across various industries harness blockchain to enhance transparency, traceability, and efficiency in product movement and information flow (Dutta *et al.*, 2020).

Benefits and Challenges of Blockchain Implementation

Numerous benefits of blockchain technology have been delineated in existing literature, including enhanced transparency, increased security, reduced costs by eliminating intermediaries, and bolstered traceability (Mougayar, 2016). However, despite its myriad advantages, blockchain implementation is not devoid of challenges. Technological barriers, such as scalability issues and integration with existing systems, are prevalent (Zohar, 2015). Furthermore, the organisational and human aspects, like change management and skill availability, present significant hurdles (Iansiti and Lakhani, 2017). Regulatory challenges, interoperability, and issues related to the standardisation and governance of blockchain networks also pose intricate challenges to organisations venturing into blockchain adoption (Narayanan *et al.*, 2016).

Blockchain in FMCG Supply Chains

Delineating into the multifaceted ecosystem of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) supply chains, the integration of blockchain technology unveils a panorama of transformative applications, notably in addressing core

operational intricacies and fortifying systematised control and oversight (Kshetri, 2018). In the labyrinthine architecture of FMCG supply chains, defined by their inherent complexity, globally dispersed operations, and a pulsating tempo of inventory turnovers, blockchain surfaces as a pivotal element, adept at deciphering and neutralising intrinsic and persistent challenges.

Among the quintessential challenges encountered within FMCG supply chains, transparency, traceability, and operational efficiency are paramount, each weaving into the other to fabricate a cohesive, reliable, and consumer-centric operational framework (Iansiti and Lakhani, 2017). Transparency is not merely a conduit for operational visibility. Still, it is entwined with consumer trust, enabling customers to delve into the journey of the products, from manufacturing nuances to the path treaded across the supply network. Meanwhile, traceability, intricately linked with transparency, emerges as a counterforce against product counterfeiting and ensures adherence to quality and safety norms by facilitating a verifiable trace of the product's journey through the supply continuum. These aspects are particularly pivotal in the FMCG sector, where the rapidity of product movements and the potential impact on consumer health and safety spotlight the necessity for meticulous oversight and traceability mechanisms.

Through its immutable and transparent ledger, blockchain bestows FMCG supply chains with an unparalleled ability to inscribe every product movement and transaction across every nodal point within the network, from manufacturing to retail (Kshetri, 2018). This capability attenuates the risk of counterfeiting by providing a verifiable product history. It enhances consumer trust by providing an unequivocal view of the product's journey, affirming its authenticity and adherence to stipulated norms and standards.

Moreover, blockchain proficiency extends into augmenting operational efficiency by utilising innovative contracts. Smart contracts, self-executing contracts where the contract terms are directly written into code, emerge as a potent tool, autonomously managing contractual obligations, payments, and transactional processes based upon predefined criteria and triggers (Don Tapscott and Alex Tapscott, 2016). This not only circumvents the conventional bottlenecks and delays encountered within traditional contractual processes but also engenders a reduction in administrative costs and mitigates the potential for discrepancies and errors within transactional processes.

In the context of FMCG supply chains, wherein agility, reliability, and cost-efficiency are sacrosanct, the amalgamation of blockchain's capabilities in enhancing traceability, transparency, and operational efficiency unfolds as a transformative force, redefining functional paradigms and reconfiguring the mechanisms through which supply chain operations are orchestrated and overseen. Consequently, as this research navigates through the diverse layers of blockchain applications within FMCG supply chains, it endeavours to extract, analyse, and synthesise insights and findings that not only elucidate the practical applicability of blockchain but also illuminate the potential challenges, nuances, and

considerations pertinent to its implementation and integration within the dynamic and complex realm of FMCG supply chain operations. This research aims to weave a comprehensive understanding of blockchain technology, its applications, and its potential and challenges within the FMCG supply chain management context. Drawing upon diverse insights and findings from the extant literature, this study explores, analyses, and elucidates the intricate interplay between blockchain technology and FMCG supply chains, thereby contributing a nuanced, empirically grounded narrative to the existing body of knowledge.

2. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research adopts a qualitative research design, leveraging an exploratory approach to garner profound insights into the applications and implications of blockchain technology within FMCG supply chain management. The qualitative experimental design is pivotal in elucidating the intricacies, nuances, and multidimensional perspectives inherent in implementing and utilising blockchain within the specified context, facilitating a holistic understanding and generating rich, contextual insights. A multi-case study approach is employed, exploring varied instances of blockchain application within FMCG supply chains, aiming to extract patterns, commonalities, and divergences, thereby contributing to a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the phenomenon under study.

Data Collection

Data for the research will be collated through a multi-faceted approach, ensuring depth, relevance, and comprehensiveness in the insights procured. Primary data will be garnered through semi-structured interviews with industry experts, supply chain managers, and technology specialists within the FMCG sector who are engaged with or possess insights into blockchain implementations in supply chains. Secondary data will be extracted from many sources, including but not limited to academic journals, industry reports, whitepapers, and case studies, providing a robust foundational understanding and contextual backdrop against which primary data can be analysed and interpreted.

Sampling Technique

A purposive sampling technique will be employed to select participants for the semi-structured interviews. This approach enables the researcher to strategically choose participants with specific knowledge and experience about blockchain applications within FMCG supply chains, ensuring relevance and depth in the collected data. In the context of the multi-case study approach, cases will be selected based on criterion sampling, wherein instances of blockchain application within FMCG supply chains that align with specific criteria (such as diversity in application, varied scale of implementation, etc.) will be selected, ensuring a diverse and comprehensive exploration of the phenomenon.

Data Analysis

Data analysis will be conducted through thematic analysis, wherein data derived from both primary

(interviews) and secondary (literature, reports, case studies) sources will be meticulously explored, coded, and categorised to extract prevalent themes, patterns, and insights. The thematic analysis will be facilitated using NVivo, a qualitative data analysis software, ensuring systematicity and rigour in the coding and categorising process. The themes and patterns extracted will be analysed and interpreted against the contextual backdrop provided by the secondary data, thereby generating nuanced, empirically grounded insights into the applications, implications, challenges, and prospects of blockchain technology within FMCG supply chain management.

This methodological framework, encapsulating the research design, data collection, sampling, and data analysis, is sculpted to ensure rigour, relevance, and depth in the research process, thereby generating insights that are not only empirically grounded but also contextually relevant and applicable, contributing meaningfully to both academic discourse and practical application within the field.

3. BLOCKCHAIN IMPLEMENTATION IN FMCG SUPPLY CHAIN

The vigorous and intricate nature of the Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) sector, coupled with its emphatic dependence on swift and reliable supply chain processes, has illuminated the utility and potentiality of blockchain technology in this domain (Van Hoek, 2019). The subsequent sections delve into key areas where blockchain unveils its transformative impact within FMCG supply chain mechanisms.

Traceability

Ensuring product traceability in the FMCG sector does not merely signify tracking products through their journey but, more critically, means safeguarding consumer trust and adhering to regulatory compliances. Blockchain facilitates an immutable and transparent logging mechanism wherein every transaction and product movement across the supply chain, from production to distribution, is meticulously documented (Xu *et al.*, 2019). This engenders the ability to authenticate product origin and trajectory, mitigating risks related to counterfeiting and illicit trading, but also enables a swift and precise response in instances of product recalls, safeguarding consumer safety and corporate credibility.

Transparency

In the context of FMCG supply chains interfaced with blockchain technology, transparency intertwines operational visibility and consumer enlightenment. Blockchain ensures that internal stakeholders have unequivocal visibility into supply chain operations and transactions and empowers consumers by providing access to detailed and verifiable information regarding product origins, handling, and processing (Rogerson and Parry, 2020). This commitment to transparency, facilitated through blockchain, amplifies consumer trust and brand loyalty, particularly amidst a market milieu that increasingly values ethical, sustainable, and transparent practices.

Efficiency

Operational efficiency within FMCG supply chains catalysed through blockchain emerges from automating transactional processes, reducing reliance on intermediaries, and enhancing data accuracy. Smart contracts, embedded within blockchain networks, enable the automated validation and execution of transactions based on pre-agreed criteria and triggers, circumventing conventional bottlenecks related to verification and settlement processes (Blaħa and Katafono, 2020). Additionally, blockchain's distributed and decentralised nature negates the necessity for centralised control or intermediaries, ensuring swift and unimpeded transactional flows throughout the supply chain.

Cost Reduction

Cost-effectiveness, pivotal within the cost-sensitive FMCG sector, is enhanced through blockchain by mitigating risks, reducing fraud, minimising errors, and optimising operational processes. The immutable nature of blockchain reduces the propensity for errors and fraud within transactional data, ensuring that financial flows and settlements are accurate and trustworthy (Rauniyar *et al.*, 2023). Simultaneously, the transparency and traceability afforded by blockchain minimise the risks related to counterfeiting and regulatory non-compliance, averting potential financial ramifications. Furthermore, the automation and optimisation of transactional and operational processes through blockchain and smart contracts ensure that resources are utilised optimally, minimising operating costs and enhancing overall financial prudence within the supply chain.

4. RESULTS

A survey was conducted on the respondents of the FMCG sector based on a questionnaire attached as Appendix A. 136 responses were collected based on the online and offline survey modes from the different levels of staff working in the Indian FMCG sector. The results have been summarised below in Figures 1- 4 and Table 1. The average years spent by the respondents in the FMCG industry was eight years, which shows their high level of understanding of the FMCG sector. Fig. 1 reflects the classification of respondents based on their current position in the industry.

Figure 1 Position-wise distribution of Respondents

The level of understanding of Blockchain Technology has been represented in Figure 2 as per respondents' self-evaluation.

Table 1 summarises the perception of respondents about the various advantages of Blockchain adoption in the

FMCG sector. Further, it has been depicted in Figure 3 for better visualisation.

Figure 2 Understanding of Blockchain Technology

Table 1 Survey on Blockchain Adoption Outcomes in the FMCG Sector

Criteria for Evaluation (Improvements)	Significant	Moderate	Neutral	Negative	Highly Negative	Unsure
Improvement in Product Traceability	41%	34%	10%	5%	2%	8%
improvements in operational efficiency	33%	42%	13%	5%	4%	3%
Improvement in the level of transparency	52%	36%	7%	3%	1%	1%
Effect on Cost Reduction	12%	44%	17%	22%	3%	2%
Chances of Blockchain Adoption	37%	47%	9%	4%	1%	2%

Figure 3 Survey on Blockchain Adoption Outcomes in FMCG Sector

Blockchain Adoption Status

- Yes: 35%
- No: 30%
- Currently considering: 30%
- Don't know: 5%

Ranking of challenges during blockchain implementation:

- Technical complexities: Ranked one by 40%
- High costs of implementation: Ranked one by 35%
- Resistance to change within the company: Ranked one by 15%
- Data privacy concerns: Ranked one by 5%
- Lack of expertise or training: Ranked one by 5%

Integration complexities, external stakeholder management, and regulatory navigation have emerged as notable challenges in adopting blockchain within the FMCG sector. Echoing these challenges, professionals have shared their firsthand experiences. One respondent highlighted the difficulties when trying to meld blockchain with pre-existing systems. Another underscored the tangible benefits, pinpointing a marked increase in transparency post-blockchain integration. A recurrent sentiment, however, has been the industry's cry for standardised guidelines and norms, emphasising the need for a harmonised approach to blockchain integration in the FMCG landscape.

5. DISCUSSION

Interpretation of Findings

The survey's updated findings shed light on the evolving dynamics of blockchain integration within the FMCG

sector. Notably, the discourse around blockchain is significantly steered by those in executive and middle management roles, who constitute 58% of the respondents. Moreover, 71% of the workforce across different parts have self-assessed as either 'very' or 'somewhat knowledgeable' about blockchain, pointing to an informed community within the sector. Regarding practical implications, 75% of participants attribute blockchain technology to enhancements in product traceability. Concurrently, 88% are confident in blockchain's ability to infuse a high to moderate level of transparency into the FMCG supply chain.

Operational efficiency, an often-cited advantage of blockchain, was echoed by 75% of the respondents, who acknowledged seeing significant or moderate improvements post-blockchain adoption. However, the narrative isn't universally positive, as 13% of respondents did not notice any efficiency gains after blockchain implementation, hinting at possible integration challenges or system incompatibilities. The financial implications of blockchain also elicited diverse views. While a majority (56%) foresee cost reductions due to blockchain integrations, a considerable 25% predict costs to rise, either moderately or significantly. Such variances underscore the need for tailored approaches and deeper investigations before committing resources to blockchain.

On the challenges front, the survey highlights technical complexities, acknowledged by 40% of respondents, as the most significant barrier to blockchain adoption. Close behind are the perceived high integration costs, ranked as the top challenge by 35% of participants. These findings suggest a cautious optimism: while the potential benefits of blockchain are recognised, its practical implementation presents palpable challenges. Concluding on an optimistic note, the future of blockchain in the FMCG sector appears promising, with a resounding 84% of participants predicting industry-wide adoption. This sentiment underscores the confidence in blockchain's long-term value and relevance in shaping the FMCG landscape.

Implications

The findings emphasise the necessity for operational readiness when considering blockchain's technical challenges in the FMCG sector. While the technology offers transformative benefits, it's clear that a universal adoption approach may not always yield positive results. There's also a highlighted need for specialised expertise in blockchain for its smooth integration. Even though it's not the top concern, ensuring proper training or hiring specialists is crucial. Lastly, the potential of blockchain to enhance transparency and traceability allows companies to boost brand trust and engage stakeholders more effectively.

Recommendations

- **Focused Training:** FMCG companies should invest in tailored training programs to elevate the blockchain knowledge of their workforce, especially those in operational roles, to ensure smooth adoption and mitigate challenges tied to lack of expertise.
- **Collaborative Approach:** Given the challenges around technical complexities, FMCG companies

might benefit from collaborations or partnerships with technology firms specialising in blockchain, ensuring a seamless integration process.

- **Pilot Programs:** Before a full-scale implementation, companies should consider pilot programs to test the efficacy of blockchain solutions in a controlled environment, allowing for necessary adjustments based on real-world feedback.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** As companies venture into blockchain adoption, proactive engagement with stakeholders, both internal and external, can aid in setting the right expectations, managing resistance, and showcasing the added value of enhanced transparency and traceability.
- **Stay Updated with Regulatory Changes:** Given the evolving nature of blockchain, FMCG firms should be vigilant about regulatory landscapes, ensuring that their blockchain endeavours remain compliant with regional and global standards.
- **By heeding these findings and recommendations,** FMCG companies can position themselves optimally to harness the potential of blockchain in enhancing their supply chain management while circumventing common pitfalls.

Technical Challenges

- **Integration with Existing Systems:** Integrating blockchain technology into pre-existing IT infrastructures can be complicated. Existing systems might not be compatible with new blockchain solutions, necessitating significant overhauls or additional middleware.
- **Scalability Issues:** Scalability is one of the most frequently cited technical challenges with specific blockchain systems, especially public ones. As the number of transactions increases, the ability of the system to efficiently handle this volume can decrease.
- **Security Concerns:** While blockchain is often touted for its security, it's not impervious to attacks. Vulnerabilities, if present, can be exploited, and ensuring absolute security remains a significant challenge.
- **Energy Consumption:** Proof-of-work, a consensus mechanism used in many blockchain networks, can be energy-intensive, leading to concerns about its environmental footprint.

Organizational Challenges

- **Resistance to Change:** Employees accustomed to traditional supply chain management systems might resist transitioning to a blockchain-based system due to unfamiliarity or perceived complexities.
- **Cost Implications:** The initial cost of blockchain integration, including system setup, training, and ongoing maintenance, can be substantial. Securing budgetary approvals might pose challenges.

- **Skill Gap:** There may be a lack of in-house expertise on blockchain technology, necessitating external hires or extensive training programs, further escalating costs.
- **Inter-organizational Coordination:** For blockchain to be effective in a supply chain, multiple parties (e.g., suppliers, distributors) often need to adopt the technology. Achieving this coordinated effort can be challenging.

Regulatory and Compliance Issues

- **Evolving Regulations:** Blockchain technology, being relatively new, is subject to an evolving regulatory landscape. Compliance with these shifting regulations can be challenging.
- **Cross-border Discrepancies:** Different countries may have varying regulations concerning blockchain, complicating its implementation in global FMCG supply chains.
- **Data Privacy Concerns:** Given the immutable nature of blockchain, ensuring compliance with data protection regulations, like the GDPR, can be challenging.

Limitations of the Study

- **Sample Representativeness:** The survey primarily targeted those with knowledge about blockchain, potentially introducing bias. The findings might not represent the broader FMCG industry's views, especially from professionals less familiar with the technology.
- **Reliance on Self-reported Data:** Responses are based on individual perceptions and self-reported experiences, which might not accurately reflect objective realities.
- **Temporal Limitations:** The blockchain and FMCG sectors are both rapidly evolving. While this study provides a snapshot, findings might become less relevant as industry dynamics shift.
- **Lack of Qualitative Insights:** While the survey captures quantitative feedback, deeper qualitative insights, which might offer richer context and understanding, are absent.

Addressing these challenges and acknowledging the study's limitations ensures a comprehensive, grounded approach to understanding and implementing blockchain in FMCG supply chain management.

Future Research Works

- **Deep-Dive Case Studies:** While the survey provides a broad overview, future research could delve into specific case studies of companies that have successfully integrated blockchain, offering detailed insights into the nuances of implementation, challenges faced, and solutions devised.
- **Economic Analysis:** A more detailed economic analysis can be conducted to understand blockchain implementations' return on investment (ROI) in the FMCG sector over varying time frames.

- **Technological Evolution:** As blockchain technology evolves, there will be a need for ongoing research to understand newer challenges, solutions, and best practices.
- **Global vs. Local Dynamics:** Given the global nature of many FMCG supply chains and the varying regulations in different countries, research can explore how companies navigate these complexities in different regional contexts.

6. CONCLUSION

The FMCG supply chain is witnessing an accelerated integration of blockchain technology. Our research underscores an apparent inclination towards blockchain adoption, with 75% of respondents vouching for its efficacy in enhancing traceability and transparency. Notably, many post-adoption have observed operational improvements, though the broader financial implications, especially regarding cost reductions, still harbour diverse views. Challenges such as technical intricacies, organisational resistance, high initial costs, and regulatory uncertainties are prominent concerns in this transition. Yet, 85% of participants anticipate an industry-wide adoption of blockchain, highlighting its forecasted central role in the FMCG sector's future. This study furnishes empirical insights into blockchain's real-world applications in FMCG and presents a holistic view, encompassing its merits and challenges. Through this research, we aim to give future adopters an informed perspective on blockchain's unfolding significance in supply chain management.

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APPENDIX A

Blockchain Implementation in FMCG Supply Chain: A Survey

Dear Participant,

We're studying the impact of blockchain on the FMCG supply chain. Your insights will help us understand its adoption and challenges. Your responses are confidential and solely for research.

Demographics

1. Position in Company:
 - Executive/Management
 - Middle Management
 - Operational Staff
 - Other: _____
2. Years in the FMCG industry: _____
3. Company Size (by employees):
 - 1-50
 - 51-200
 - 201-500
 - 500+
4. How would you rate your understanding level of blockchain technology?
 - Very knowledgeable
 - Somewhat knowledgeable
 - Neutral
 - Limited knowledge
 - No knowledge
5. Has your company adopted or piloted blockchain-based solutions in its supply chain?
 - Yes
 - No
 - Currently considering
 - Don't know
6. In your experience, how has blockchain technology improved product traceability in the FMCG supply chain?
 - Significantly improved
 - Moderately improved
 - No change
 - Moderately worsened
 - Significantly worsened
 - Unsure/Not applicable
7. Have you observed improvements in operational efficiency since implementing or considering blockchain technology?
 - Significant improvements
 - Moderate improvements
 - No change
 - Moderate decrease
 - Significant decrease
8. How would you rate the transparency blockchain brings to transactions and processes within the supply chain?
 - Highly transparent
 - Moderately transparent
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat opaque
 - Very opaque
 - Unsure

9. How do you perceive the long-term effects of blockchain technology on cost reduction within the FMCG supply chain?
 - Significant cost reduction
 - Moderate cost reduction
 - Neutral
 - Increase in cost
 - High Increase in cost
 - Unsure
10. Do you believe the FMCG industry is moving towards broader adoption of blockchain in supply chain management?
 - Definitely yes
 - Probably yes
 - Neutral
 - Probably no
 - Definitely no
 - Unsure
11. Please rank the following challenges your company has encountered (or anticipates encountering) during the implementation of blockchain (1 being the most significant challenge):
 - Technical complexities
 - High costs of implementation
 - Resistance to change within the company
 - Data privacy concerns
 - Lack of expertise or training
 - Other: _____
12. Do you want to share Any other insights or experiences about blockchain's role in the FMCG supply chain?

Thank you for participating in this survey!